

G-CONTROL FATIGUE TESTING OF DEBONDED SANDWICH COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The G-control technique is a new testing methodology which allows fatigue crack growth characterization of sandwich specimens using real-time control of the cyclic energy release rate. A compliance based measurement method is used to monitor the crack length to maintain a constant energy release rate at the crack tip during the fatigue test. MMB sandwich specimens with GFRP face sheets and H100 and H160 PVC foam cores were tested, showing approximately constant crack propagation rate.

1 Introduction

Sandwich composites are nowadays used in large and light structures, where each of the constituent materials are highly stressed. Typically, aircrafts and wind turbines are subject to cyclic loads and are required to withstand a large number of loading cycles without substantial damage or structural failure. A sandwich structure made from polymer composite face sheets over a polymer foam typically contains small, undetected manufacturing flaws in the form of face/core debonds. It is of primary importance, thus, to study the behavior of the structure under fatigue loading. Several studies on fatigue crack propagation of face/core interface debonds have been presented, e.g. [1-3]. Common to all these studies is that the cyclic loading was conducted under load or displacement control, i.e. the maximum and minimum displacements or loads were kept constant during fatigue cycling. As illustrated in Fig. 1, a typical test specimen under cyclic loading with constant displacement amplitude will experience retardation of crack growth, while constant load amplitude leads to accelerated crack

growth (although there are exceptions to this rule, see Ref. [3]). A specimen where cyclic energy release rate (ΔG) is held constant is expected to display constant cyclic crack growth rate (da/dN). Such a test approach is highly desirable. This is a relatively new technique which has become possible due to advanced computer controlled test systems. This method allows testing at constant crack growth rate and avoids any influence from path history effects (kinking, interlayer deflection etc.) related to the change of energy release rate level, which must be taken into account with the traditional displacement and load control testing methods.

The main objective of this work is to develop the G-control technique to allow fatigue crack growth characterization of sandwich face/core interfaces using real-time control of the energy release rate.

The implementation of this concept on a MTS Table-Top hydraulic test machine with the MTS Test Suite software will be described. The concept will be experimentally demonstrated on a debonded sandwich specimen with fiberglass face sheets and H45, H100 and H160 PVC foam cores.

2 Test specimen

Fatigue crack growth of face/core interface cracks, Fig. 1, is considered here. Several sandwich fatigue test specimens have been developed for studying face/core crack growth. The CSB (Cracked Sandwich Beam) and DCB (Double Cantilever Beam) specimens are used to perform tests under mode I and mode II [4-5]. Mixed mode fracture and fatigue tests have been performed using the mixed mode bending (MMB) specimen [2]. This specimen is shown in Fig. 2.

Through a system of saddle, roller and hinges, the load transferred to the specimen is split into a

combination of tensile normal (mode I) and sliding shear (mode II) loadings at the crack tip. By adjusting the position of the load application point, i.e. loading lever distance, c , in Fig. 2, this test allows control of the mode mixity. The mode mixity is quantified by the mode mixity phase angle [7], which defines the relative amount of sliding and opening displacements. Determination of the phase angle requires finite element analysis as described in Ref. [8].

The compliance of the MMB specimen is given by the following expression [6],

$$C = \left[\frac{c}{L} C_{DCB_upper} + \frac{c-L}{2L} C_{DCB_lower} \right] \left(\frac{c}{L} - \alpha \frac{c+L}{2L} \right) + \left(\frac{c+L}{L} \right)^2 C_{CSB} \quad (1)$$

where c and L are the loading lever distance and half span length, Fig. 2, and α is the load partitioning factor. This factor and C_{DCB_upper} , C_{DCB_lower} and C_{CSB} are defined in Ref. [6].

The energy release rate G for the MMB specimen is given by

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (2)$$

where P is the load applied, a is the crack length and b is the specimen width. Combination of Eqs. (1) and (2) yields

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2b^2} \left(\frac{c}{L} \left(\frac{c}{L} - \alpha \frac{c+L}{2L} \right) \frac{12}{E_f h_f^3} \left[a^2 + 2a\eta^{1/4} + \eta^{1/2} \right] + \frac{c-L}{2L} \left(\frac{c}{L} - \alpha \frac{c+L}{2L} \right) \left[\frac{1}{h_c G_{xz}} + \frac{a^2}{\left(D - \frac{B^2}{A} \right)} \right] + \left(\frac{c+L}{L} \right)^2 \left(\frac{a^2}{8} \left[\frac{1}{D_{debonded}} - \frac{1}{D_{intact}} \right] \right) \right) \quad (3)$$

where the new symbols introduced are E_f , Young's modulus of the face, h_f , thickness of the face, η , elastic foundation parameter, h_c , thickness of the core, G_{xz} , shear modulus of the core, A , B , D are respectively the extensional, coupling and bending stiffnesses for a sandwich beam. $D_{debonded}$ and D_{intact} are the bending stiffnesses of the debonded and intact regions of the specimen.

Since a cyclic test is considered, it is convenient to introduce the concept of "cyclic energy release rate", ΔG

$$\Delta G = \frac{P_{max}^2 - P_{min}^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (4)$$

which is the range of energy release rate calculated for each cycle using the maximum and minimum values of the load and crack length.

3 G-control of fatigue test

In order to maintain a constant cyclic ΔG during the fatigue tests, the maximum and minimum displacement are continuously monitored and automatically adjusted during the crack propagation while maintaining a constant cyclic load ratio $R = \delta_{min}/\delta_{max}$

Fig. 3 shows a schematic representation of the G-control loop. Before starting the test a desired range of energy release rate and R ratio are set. The initial crack length, a , is determined from the measured compliance, and the maximum and minimum loads required for Eq. (4) are obtained from

$$P = \frac{\delta}{C} \quad (5)$$

where the measured δ is δ_{max} and δ_{min} , respectively. Notice that $\delta_{min} = R \delta_{max}$. During the cyclic test the compliance is continuously monitored from the load and displacement signals. The crack length is calculated from the compliance and ΔG is calculated from Eq. (4). The actual ΔG value is compared to the desired value. If the two values are equal (within a certain range), the cyclic displacement amplitudes remain, otherwise they are adjusted in order to reach the desired G level.

4 Code implementation into machine controller

An MTS Table-Top 10 kN test machine with servo-hydraulic actuator and 10 kN load cell was used for the fatigue tests. The G-control code was implemented into MTS TestSuite Multipurpose Elite, a very flexible software which allows programming and complex testing through a drag-and-drop toolbox including a wide choice of functions [9].

The G-control method is based on several important functions. “*Assign variables*” is used to assign a value to a variable. It can be either a number or a formula (which can include other variables as well). “*Cycle + DAQ*” consists of sine wave cycling with incorporated data acquisition process. Maximum and minimum values of the cyclic displacement, δ_{\max} and δ_{\min} can be changed automatically during the test. “*Calculate Variables*” is used to make calculations during cycling, in order to evaluate if some of the variables need to be adjusted. “*While-Loop Activity*” allows to repeat continuously the same operations (cyclic loading + variables calculations). “*If-Else Condition*” is actually the heart of the G-control code. It allows to evaluate if ΔG is above or below the desired level.

In order to initialize the test, few steps are needed. First the specimen geometry and material properties are input into the code, as well as the desired ΔG level, which must be kept constant during the test, and the R ratio. A crack length vs compliance relation is obtained through the closed-form formulas described in section 2. A curve fit equation is then used as input into the code.

Last but not least step before starting the test, maximum and minimum initial displacement have to be input. It is suggested to use small initial displacement values resulting in a G level below the desired one. In fact, the code is built in order to increase (not decrease) the displacement every time ΔG falls below the predefined level.

5 Experimental tests

MMB specimens with two sets of sandwich composite materials, both with quasi-isotropic GFRP face sheets and H45, H100 and H160 PVC foam cores, were prepared. The face and core materials have been subject to several mechanical

tests (tensile, compression and shear tests) to determine in-plane and out-of-plane mechanical properties, such as Young’s modulus, Poisson ratio and shear modulus. All nine orthotropic elastic constants of the face sheets are measured for the purpose of subsequent detailed FE analysis.

12 sandwich specimens with GFRP face sheets (6 with H100 foam core and 6 with H160 foam core) were prepared.

The MMB specimens were pre-cracked using a band saw to achieve a 30-40 mm long crack at the face-core interface (Fig. 4). The band saw method was found to be more efficient method to achieve a pre-crack than the traditional Teflon film insert, which was very often leading to crack kinking into the face.

After pre-cracking, the specimens were tested under mixed mode loading (mode I dominant) through a wide range of energy release rate levels, in order to evaluate crack propagation rate.

Displacement (max and min) and load (max and min) signals are recorded during the test for each cycle through the data acquisition process. During the test, several parameters are displayed on the computer screen in real time, such as current ΔG level, crack length and compliance.

Tests started at a low ΔG level by fatigue cycling of the specimen for about 300 cycles. If no crack propagation occurred, ΔG was increased and 300 cycles were applied again, and so on. When crack propagation was observed, the test would be carried on for several thousands of cycles, in order to propagate the crack 10 – 15 mm.

6. Test results

Fig. 5 shows an example of G-controlled test, where the target has been set equal to $\Delta G = 190 \text{ J/m}^2$. The red dotted line represents the actual ΔG and the blue continuous line shows δ_{\max} . It can be seen that when ΔG falls slightly below the predefined level, the maximum displacement magnitude is increased by a small step (in this case 0.5 mm) and ΔG increases. It is evident in Fig. 5 that ΔG is not perfectly constant, being subject to oscillations (in this case the variation is about $7 - 8 \text{ J/m}^2$). In order to minimize the variation, the displacement increment can be reduced.

Fig. 6 shows crack length and compliance during the cyclic crack propagation test. It can be seen how, after a transient period of about 50 cycles where the crack does not propagate because the displacement applied to the specimen is too small, the crack grows at approximately constant speed.

Concluding Remarks

A newly developed G-control testing methodology which allows fatigue crack growth characterization of sandwich specimens using real-time control of the cyclic energy release rate was demonstrated using the sandwich MMB specimen. A compliance based measurement method was used to monitor the crack length to maintain a constant energy release rate at the crack tip during the fatigue test. MMB sandwich specimens with GFRP face sheets and H100 and H160 PVC foam cores were tested, showing approximately constant crack propagation rate.

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Tables and Figures

Fig. 1. Crack length vs number of cycles for different testing modes, i.e. displacement (δ) control, energy release rate (G) control and load (P) control.

Fig. 2. MMB test rig and specimen

Fig. 4. Specimen pre-cracked using band saw.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of G-control code

Fig. 5. Maximum displacement and energy release rate vs cycles for a specimen with H45 core.

Fig. 6. Crack length and compliance vs cycles during fatigue test of a sandwich specimen with H45 core.